

Dr. Ambedkar Vision on Employment & Social Security

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Abstract

In this paper we will discuss about the history of employment exchange in India and Ambedkar's role in establishing employment exchanges and his view on India's development and labour welfare. B. R. Ambedkar contributed significantly to many policies for the welfare of people in general and for the labour working class in particular; many such policies are unknown not only to the general public, but also to intellectuals.

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Introduction :

In this paper we will discuss about the history of employment exchange in India and Ambedkar's role in establishing employment exchanges and his view on India's development and labour welfare. B. R. Ambedkar contributed significantly to many policies for the welfare of people in general and for the labour/ working class in particular; many such policies are unknown not only to the general public, but also to intellectuals. Whether this ignorance is by design or by chance, is not clear. In this unit we will explore Ambedkar's works as a savior of the labour or working class. Ambedkar was a trained economist; he studied economics throughout his student life. He earned major degrees such as MA, MSc, Ph.D. and D.Sc. in economics from reputed universities abroad. He not only studied economics but also used what he learnt for the welfare of the general population of this country. Among those who studied abroad in his times, he was perhaps the only Indian who chose the problems of Indian economy as topics for his research. Some of his major research works related to Indian economy are:

- Administration and Finance of East India Company
- Provincial Finance of British India
- The Problem of the Rupee's

As a labour leader he worked with the Bombay cotton mill workers and later founded the Independent Labour Party (1936). As a Labour Member of the Viceroy's Executive Council from 1942 to 1946 and after, Ambedkar played important roles in changing the fortunes of millions of labourers in this country. He introduced many welfare measures that provide a safety net for the working class, even now. The following are some important measures:

- Establishment of employment exchanges
- Mechanism to fix minimum wages
- Tripartite dispute settlement mechanism
- Fixation of working hours
- Maternity leave for female employees

- Improving the working conditions of female employees
- Leave with pay.

Ambedkar was of the opinion that a legitimate remuneration, comfortable working hours, good working conditions, a sense of security at the workplace and proper dispute redressal mechanisms will not only increase the productivity of labour, but will also ensure a legitimate share of labour in the total production or income of the respective industry. He also contributed to bringing in provisions and policies for promoting skill development of workers in India. He was of the opinion that skill development should be part of the mainstream education. He believed that technical education to Dalits is very important to break the caste hegemony in this country.

He believed that a structured system was necessary to tackle unemployment, so an organised system of records and accountability was necessary to create an environment for achieving the goal of creating quality employment to an ever-increasing working population. Subsequently the National Employment Agency (Employment Exchange) came into being in this country.

No plan for the future development of the country can be deemed to be complete which does not provide for technical and scientific training. This is the age of machine and it is only those countries in which technical and scientific training has risen to the highest pitch that will survive in the struggle that will commence when the war is over, for maintaining decent standards of living for their people.

These views were expressed by Ambedkar while addressing the Technical Training Scheme Advisory Committee in Calcutta on 24 August 1944 in his capacity as the Labour Member, Government of India. The question facing the committee was the future of skilled labour, trained during the war for induction in the army, after the war and there-structuring of the technical training system. Ambedkar was of the view that technical training and skill development should not only be maintained but extended all over the country. He advocated making it an integral part of India's educational system. He was very particular about the ability and willingness of the industry to absorb the trainees as an essential condition of success of this program. He understood that there was a mismatch between the skills imparted to the trainees in the government centres and the requirements of the industry. The civil industry preferred to hire untrained workmen in large numbers and train them in job-specific skills over time. Ambedkar understood the need for collaboration and feedback system between government training centres and the industry; he proposed that training courses be tailored accordingly to ensure greater employability.

His immediate concern was the employability of the veterans from the technical wing of the army, who had been trained to meet war requirements. He was of the view that a failure to absorb them into meaningful employment would only mean that 'we have won the war, but done nothing for the peace'. Since the rate of absorption in civil industry was less than what was desirable, Ambedkar proposed the following:

- modifications in the training
- changes in the syllabus
- Introduction of new subsidiary courses.

This is relevant even today when there is wide gap between the education system and employability of the students. The flexibility and openness of Ambedkar, lacking in the education system today, can synchronize the skills imparted and the skills needed by the labour force of the country. To this day, our education system lacks the flexibility and openness advocated by Ambedkar to harmonise the skills imparted by our education system with those needed by industry. His advocacy to introduce new subsidiary courses resonates with the concept of vocational courses and value-added courses today. In fact, Ambedkar's views on the necessity of skill development and technical training emanate from his understanding of the caste system, apart from the need of the modern age. Unlike others who characterized the caste system as a system of division of labour, Ambedkar saw it as a system of division of labourers who are compartmentalized into water-tight categories with no vertical or horizontal movement. People are clubbed indifferent castes according to their respective professions, which are then arranged, in a graded hierarchy. The central point in the caste system has been the denial of economic freedom i.e. freedom to choose one's profession, which is determined by birth. This denial of economic freedom has been further imposed via denial of opportunity to change the profession for want of requisite technical skills and education. This is because access to education, skill development and technical training has been denied to the masses under the disabilities imposed by the caste system. In his opinion, to create avenues for social mobility, professional mobility was the first condition and to ensure professional mobility, access to education and skill development was a must. Only when Dalit and oppressed castes leave their ancestral professions and move into modern professions of the emerging economy, can there be an improvement in their socio-economic status. This also made Ambedkar a supporter of industrialisation, unlike Gandhi, who romanticized the village economy.

Ambedkar points out that:

Stratification of occupations which is the result of the caste system is positively pernicious. Industry is never static; it undergoes rapid and abrupt changes. With such changes an individual must be free to change his occupation.

But for this to happen, the first step was to ensure the spread of basic education, technical training and skill development among the masses. On 29 October 1942, Ambedkar submitted a Memorandum on the Grievances of the Scheduled Castes to the Governor-General of India. The memorandum presented the political, educational and other grievances of the scheduled castes with detailed facts and figures. He highlighted that education of science and technology was very low among the scheduled castes. This was mainly due to the high cost of accessing such education. Education in arts and law were not of much benefit to the scheduled castes because with these qualifications, chances of securing employment were low. The courses in science and technology promised greater certainty of jobs but were out of their reach. He proposed creating the following scholarships:

an annual grant of Rs. 2 lakh for scheduled caste students taking science and technology courses at universities or other scientific and technical training institutions in India.

an annual grant of Rs 1 lakh for scholarships in foreign universities in England, the Dominions, in Europe and America.

The members of the scheduled castes occupy the lowest rung of the economic system due to various social disabilities imposed upon them for centuries. Ambedkar says, 'In times of prosperity he is last to be employed, and in times of depression he is first to be discharged'. Ambedkar believed that with appropriate technical training and skill development, this situation can be reversed. It can not only ensure greater surety of employment in the modern economy but also greater safety of tenure. Ambedkar believed that government intervention is required to raise the level of technical education among the masses and that government support and policy can play a central role in skill development in the country. He proposed a system of apprenticeship for scheduled caste boys in undertakings run or controlled by the Government of India. He specifically highlighted the opportunities of apprenticeship in government printing presses and railway workshops.

Providing social security to the people is a big challenge in the present globalised economies. It is not an aberration that all the emerging economies in the world are striving to provide decent and improved living conditions to their people in this development world. To realise this dream of attaining social security and social welfare, the state should play a proactive role. India being a multi-cultural and multi-diversified country, it is very pertinent to address the social security issues. The social security and social welfare are very crucial as the country has many disadvantaged sections. Moreover, social security is one of the important aspects to deal with in the context of people welfare and security of life. Social security is pivotal to the present development phenomena. Social security is the protection that a society provides to individuals and households to ensure access to health care and to guarantee income security, particularly in cases of old age, unemployment, sickness, invalidity, work injury, maternity or loss of a breadwinner. Social security impacts all levels of society. It provides workers and their families' access to health care and protection against loss of income.

Social security is an important component of people's welfare. Every developing and developed economy is trying to provide certain and definite social security measures and provisions to its people. In India, provision of social protection is enshrined in the following articles of the Constitution of India as a part of the Directive Principles of State Policy:

Article 38 (securing a social order for the promotion of welfare of the people)

Article 39 (the state shall direct its policy towards securing)

- An adequate means of livelihood for its citizens
- Distribution of resources of the community to sub serve the common good
- equal pay for equal work for both men and women

Article 41 (right to work, education and public assistance)

Article 42 (just and humane conditions of work and maternity relief) and

Article 43 (to secure to all workers, work and a living wage).

Social security, poverty alleviation and social welfare measures are being implemented by various departments of state governments and by civil society organisations. Social security is of two types:

Social assistance: Provides benefits to persons, usually from a vulnerable group of community such as children, mothers, disabled and old age people, from general revenues of the state. It is non-contributory.

Social insurance: Provides benefits to persons by means of contributions of beneficiaries with contribution and subsidies from employer and state. Social security or social welfare depends upon the structure and nature of the country. A country like India, characterised by vast diversities and divisions needs social security measures that can address all people, irrespective of class, caste, gender and so on.

As the first law minister of independent India, Ambedkar proposed social security measures for the marginalised, women and factory workers. He believed that the state can help in creating wealth but creating social security for needy people was a big task even for the state. In the Indian Labour Conference on 27 November 1942, he proposed for the first time reducing working hours from 12 hours to 8 hours. He proposed equal pay for equal work irrespective of gender. He framed many laws for women labour in India such as:

Mines Maternity Benefit Act, 1941

Women labour welfare fund

Women and child labour protection act

Maternity benefit for women labour (Maternity Benefit Act, 1961)

Restoration of Ban on Employment of Women on Underground Work in Coal Mines.

For the benefit of workers, he enacted the Employees State Insurance Act, 1948 to help them with medical care, medical leave, and compensation for injuries that happen during work. The benefits provided under this act are:λSickness benefit, extended sickness benefit, and enhanced sickness benefit

Disablement benefit

Dependants' benefit

Maternity benefit

Medical benefit

Confinement expenses

Funeral expenses

Vocational rehabilitation

Physical rehabilitation

Unemployment allowance.

Some of his other contributions were:

Dearness Allowance (DA)

Holidays with pay for factory workers

Provident Fund Act

Revision of scale of pay for employees.

Many of the important social welfare schemes now extant were articulated by Ambedkar long ago.

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